

Sensitivity Testing and Logit Analysis: Two Recent Armaments Engineering Case-Studies

Douglas M. Ray, US Army RDECOM - ARDEC

Eli S. Golden, US Army RDECOM - ARDEC

Christopher Drake, US Army RDECOM - ARDEC

Key Words: Binary Logistic Regression, Logit Analysis, Design of Experiments, Sequential Testing, D-Optimal, Quantal Response-Curve

SUMMARY & CONCLUSIONS

Efficient statistical techniques for designing and analyzing experiments are often misunderstood or underutilized, despite possessing great potential when well-informed decision-making and significant cost-savings are desired. Destructive testing with binary response data is a ‘worst-case’ scenario with regards to cost and efficiency; however, in armaments engineering (especially with explosives, energetic mixes, propellants, pyrotechnics, and other one-shot devices) binary response data is often all that is available. This paper illustrates modern methods and best-practices to employ when dealing with these types of analyses, and contrasts two very different types of testing strategies applied to the munitions used in training and battle by the Warfighter.

First, we introduce the topic of test design and experimentation. To motivate the subject and illustrate some basic aspects of sensitivity testing, we present an example common to the general public: impact-resistant cases for *smart-phones*.

Next, we elaborate on some of the finer details of Logit Analysis/Binary Logistic Regression and Generalized Linear Models (GLM), while highlighting some of the mathematical underpinnings inherent in these methods.

An overview of testing strategies follows, which compares some of the different methods available for data generation. These methods can be roughly divided into two groups – those dealing with pre-manufactured test samples, and those where sequential testing is an option. Sequential tests are generally applicable when the stress level of interest is adjustable during the test’s execution, which, with regard to sample size, allows for a more efficient test.

Then we detail two recent successful examples in armament munitions testing: one where sequential testing was not possible (9mm ammunition propellant critical threshold development), and one where sequential testing was utilized (NMT - Networked Munition Technology).

Finally, we discuss some best-practices, limitations, and rules-of-thumb to be mindful of when considering these methods for different applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the most basic terms, we test (experiment) to accumulate raw data on a system or process, with the goal of processing that raw data into actionable information. Our end-state is to make informed, fact-based decisions predicated on the information gathered. In test planning we often have a multitude of options with a variety of methods and techniques at our disposal. As a tester designing experiments, there are many important considerations to keep in mind, including: Sample Size (n), Statistical Power ($1-\beta$), Confidence ($1-\alpha$), population parameters (such as mean μ and standard deviation σ in the case of Normally Distributed data), factors, levels, test order, etc.

The most effective and efficient methods are ones which enable testers to meet their test objectives (best quality of information) using the fewest samples (and smallest expenditure of resources) possible. When assessing our options for statistical methods in test planning, the method which allows the tester to achieve the test objectives (robust) with the fewest samples should be the first choice most often.

To illustrate the utility and potential that properly designed experimentation can offer, consider a hypothetical example in which a startup company seeks to deliver robust, impact-resistant *smartphone* cases to customers.

Company A would like to demonstrate 99% impact resistance (reliability) at some height (stress-level). Using a simple sample-size method, which can be calculated in MS Excel, this company would need to procure 231 phones (at \$600 ea) for testing at the single specified height of interest in order to demonstrate the desired 99% reliability with 90% confidence. The equation as used in MS Excel can be seen below:

$$=CHINVT(1-c, 2*(x+1))/((1-R)*2)$$

(where $x=0$ failures, $c=90\%$ confidence (.90), and $R=99\%$ reliability (.99)) In this equation, ‘ $2*(x+1)$ ’ represents the degrees of freedom.

Another option is a ‘static’ Logit test – where testers will drop phones at different heights between 6.0-10.5 feet in increments of 0.5 feet, with 5 units dropped at each height. This approach requires 50 phones total to complete the testing.

This saves our startup company \$114,000 in test asset usage and yields much better information, allowing us to model survival probability across the entire range of drop heights.

In this hypothetical experiment, testers drop one unit at each height (randomized) before replicating the entire sequence. After completing the fourth drop for each height in the range, the testers become confident that their results are statistically ‘stable’, and conclude the testing in 40 runs instead of the planned 50.

Furthermore, in this scenario it is possible to leverage sequential testing, since we can adjust drop-height in real-time during test execution. Using a sequential test strategy will enable the testers to potentially save even more resources – possibly even reducing sample size to 15-20 phones.

Height (Ft)	Breakage (f) Count	n	f/n
6.0	0	4	0.00
6.5	0	4	0.00
7.0	0	4	0.00
7.5	0	4	0.00
8.0	1	4	0.25
8.5	2	4	0.50
9.0	3	4	0.75
9.5	3	4	0.75
10.0	4	4	1.00
10.5	4	4	1.00

Figure 1 - Smartphone Case test data

Figure 2 - Smartphone Case frequency data

2 ANALYSIS METHODS & TEST STRATEGIES

A distinction must be made between test strategies (data collection methods) and data analysis methods.

Assuming no experimental error or system variation is present, there would exist some critical stress-level ‘x-crit’ for a binary response such that all responses to the left are 0 (or 1) and all responses to the right are 1 (or 0, respectively). This is not a realistic assumption however, and in reality we obtain data that follows a sigmoidal curve where the 50th percentile (median) gives the critical stress level (the inflection point), with the slope of the curve being tied to the variability in the system and experimental error. From a slightly different perspective, there exists some stress value x-crit to the left of

which a single unit will respond to some stimulus (or not), and to the right of which it will not (or will). It is in this way that all sensitivity data is considered to be either left- or right-censored.

Figure 3 - Smartphone Case data – reliability (survival) modeled with CI’s

Table of Survival Probabilities			
80.0% Fiducial CI			
Stress	Probability	Lower	Upper
4.0	0.999989	0.999687	1.000000
4.5	0.999963	0.999243	1.000000
5.0	0.999872	0.998168	1.000000
5.5	0.999560	0.995559	1.000000
6.0	0.998488	0.989232	0.999998
6.5	0.994817	0.973957	0.999988
7.0	0.982383	0.937654	0.999903
7.5	0.941867	0.854964	0.99265
8.0	0.824790	0.683981	0.94973

Figure 4 - Smartphone Case Data –Survival Probabilities w. 90% LCB’s at different drop heights

Regardless of the test strategy, the analysis methods used belong to a family of statistical tools called Generalized Linear Models. Logit/Probit Analysis, Logistic Regression (Binary, Ordinal, Nominal, Multiple), Poisson Regression, and Negative-Binomial Regression are all methods which belong to this family [1]. All of these methods use Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) to estimate regression model parameters (coefficients $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \dots$).

In Logit/Probit Analysis/Binary Logistic Regression, there are a number of underlying distributions we may use to model the ‘censored’ data, each relying on different ‘link’ functions (transformation function) [2]. The Logistic Model (1), and ‘Logit-link’ (2) function are often ideal as they are mathematically ‘flexible’ and allow for meaningful interpretation (provides estimate of odds-ratio for each predictor in the model), whereas Probit Analysis is similar to the Logit Analysis except that a Normal Distribution is assumed. There are several factors that influence the decision as to which underlying distribution adequately models the data

– mainly prior knowledge, and interpretation of the diagnostics such as the goodness-of-fit tests, regression table, and AICc (Akaike Information Criterion-corrected).

$$\pi(x) = \frac{e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots}}{1 + e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots}} \quad (1)$$

$$g(x) = \ln \left\{ \frac{\pi(x)}{1 - \pi(x)} \right\} \quad (2)$$

Applying the Logit transformation (2) to the Logistic regression model yields an interesting relationship (3), (4), given the fact that we are able to maintain many of the desirable properties of Linear Regression (5).

$$\text{Since: } 1 - \pi(x) = 1 - \frac{e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2}}{1 + e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2}} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2}} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{And: } g(x) = \ln \left\{ \frac{\frac{e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2}}{1 + e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2}}}{\frac{1}{1 + e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2}}} \right\} = \ln \left\{ e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2} \right\} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Therefore: } = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 \quad (5)$$

Regarding test strategies, there are two primary groups: sequential testing, and ‘static’ designs (when sequential testing is not possible due to a limitation requiring samples to be manufactured prior to testing).

The stress-levels of the most interest and usability when developing the regression model generally lie within the ‘Zone of Mixed Results’ (ZMR). This can be loosely defined as the region between the ~1st and ~99th percentiles, usually centered about the 50th percentile. The most efficient static tests target this region, and the most efficient sequential methods target the optimal leverage points at ~18th and ~82nd percentiles.

3 TWO RECENT ARMAMENTS ENGINEERING EXAMPLES

The methods mentioned herein are applied routinely in armaments engineering and munitions testing. Two recent examples are highlighted to contrast the two primary test strategies available: static, and sequential testing.

3.1 Static Testing: 9mm Ammunition Manufacturing - Propellant Critical Threshold Development

A 9mm contractor strongly felt that the specification requirement (5 grains of propellant) for a critical defect due to low weight propellant was incorrect. They offered to conduct testing to identify the point at which bullets-in-bore (BIBs) actually occur in both the M9 pistol (militarized Beretta model 92), and the Heckler & Koch (H&K) Mp5 sub-machine gun.

Because they believed the point at which BIBs were likely to occur was lower than 5.0 grains, their goal was to lower the specification requirement for critical defects, while still addressing anything below 5.0 grains as a major defect. In other words, any cartridges found with propellant loads < 5.0 grains to the point at which BIBs were found to occur as a

result of the test would be classified major defects and not require a high-cost plant shutdown. This would result in less cost to the Government/Contractor and more ammunition being delivered to the soldiers by avoiding unnecessary production and delivery delays for defects, which did not truly fit the definition of critical.

After confirming the test’s success (via model fit diagnostics) and stakeholders deciding on the desired reliability (99.9%) of defects escaping (<1/1,000 at 90% Confidence), the modeled event probabilities (from the regression model (6) and CI’s) and table of percentiles pointed towards reducing the threshold to 4.5 grains on the conservative end (ie. lower consumer/Warfighter risk).

Validation testing was conducted after this experiment at 4.25 and 4.50 grains with several hundred rounds, confirming the results and conclusions obtained initially.

$$P(BIB) = \frac{e^{11.89 - 4.69 * Grains + 1.83 * WpnType}}{1 + e^{11.89 - 4.69 * Grains + 1.83 * WpnType}} \quad (6)$$

Figure 5 - Modeled Event Probabilities with CI's, & probability plot

3.2 Sequential Testing: Networked-Munition Technology & Langlie Method

Networked-Munition Technology (NMT) is a detection/deterrent surveillance system for military outposts where trip-lines are used to actuate flare launch via a solenoid. The goal of the flare launch is to alert the Warfighter to enemy presence and deter enemy forces from proceeding toward allied positions. The flare is initiated by an electric current delivered to the solenoid switch which launches the firing pin into the percussion primer. The typical operating current is ~5.1A, and the expected minimum current under normal operating conditions is ~3.7A.

The goal of testing was to estimate the system’s performance by predicting flare functional reliability at 3.7A with some degree of confidence, and model reliability across the potential range of currents using up to 34 available samples.

A transformed-response was desired in order to minimize misfires and range shutdowns, also very little prior

information was available to help predetermine the underlying distribution and the ZMR location, thus a Langlie [4] algorithm was used. The Langlie method is not necessarily the most efficient sequential method (compared to variants of the Robbins-Monro [3], or Wu's QRC method [6]), but has some advantages when there is little prior information. The only assumption which is required to run the Langlie method are setting the upper and lower bounds of the stress range. In the case where no reversals are observed after several runs, the algorithm suggests the next test point be taken outside of the ZMR to re-converge to the 50th percentile.

The Langlie method starts off simply – halfway between the upper and lower stress bounds. If the response is negative (“0”), the next point is halfway between the upper bound and the last stress-level tested. Similarly, if the response is positive (“1”), the next point is halfway between the lower bound and the last stress-level tested, and so on.

Upon completion of testing (34 units were on-hand, and all were consumed in this test) the reliability at 3.7A was estimated to be 92% at a 90% LCB based on the modeled event probabilities (7).

$$P(\text{Fire}) = \frac{e^{-14.6245 + 491276 * \text{Current}}}{1 + e^{-14.6245 + 491276 * \text{Current}}} \quad (7)$$

Figure 6 - Modeled event probabilities with 3.7A threshold

4 SUMMARY OF BEST-PRACTICES AND LIMITATIONS

As is the case with many statistical methods, misuse of sensitivity testing is a possibility. Below are some basic ground-rules to apply when adapting these techniques for different systems:

1. Continuous response data and a classical Design of Experiments approach are always preferred. Binary response data is a last-resort solution when continuous data measurements are not available.
2. Gather as much information and historical data as possible in test planning to determine the zone of mixed results (ZMR), population parameters, underlying distribution, etc.
3. Be conservative when extrapolating the model and estimating beyond the region tested.
4. Validation testing is always recommended to confirm the

regression model.

5. Power & Sample Size Analysis – no rigorous method exists; however, simulation-based methods leveraging estimates from historical data are useful.

Logistic regression methods are powerful, but must be tailored to the individual test event. Neyer's D-Optimal [5] method (via his commercially available 'Sentest' software) is often used by engineers designing energetics. This method, along with many of the older methods, deals with only a single stress factor. This restriction could be considered a major limitation, especially when interactions may be of interest. Recent advances in sequential experimental design are now exploring methods devised for incorporating multiple stress factors into the test using Generalized Linear Models and Bayesian estimation [7].

REFERENCES

1. P. McCullagh, J. A. Nelder, *Generalized Linear Models*, Chapman & Hall CRC, 1989
2. A. Agresti, *Categorical Data Analysis*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2002
3. V. R. Joseph, Y. Tian, C.F. J. Wu, *Adaptive Designs for Stochastic Root-Finding*, Statistica Sinica, 2007
4. H. J. Langlie, *A Reliability Test Method for 'One-Shot' Items*, Technical Report U-1792, Ford Motor Company, 1965.
5. B. T. Neyer, A D-Optimality-Based Sensitivity Test, *Technometrics*, 36, 61–70 1994.
6. C. F. J. Wu, *Efficient Sequential Designs With Binary Data*, *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 80, 974–984, 1985.
7. D. C. Woods, S. M. Lewis, J. A. Eccleston, and K. G. Russell, *Designs for Generalized Linear Models With Several Variables and Model Uncertainty*, *Technometrics*, 48, 284–292 2006.
8. MIL-STD-331, Appendix D.

BIOGRAPHIES

Douglas M. Ray
 Statistical Methods & Analysis Group
 Building 92, QE&SA – Reliability Management Branch
 US Army RDECOM-ARDEC
 Picatinny Arsenal, NJ 07806-5000
 e-mail: douglas.m.ray.civ@mail.mil

Douglas Ray is the Lead Statistician in the Armaments Research, Development and Engineering Center (ARDEC) Statistical Methods & Analysis Group, located within the Quality Engineering Directorate's Reliability Management Branch. Prior to being hired at Picatinny Arsenal, NJ in 2006, Doug was an Airborne Infantry NCO and Long-Range Reconnaissance Team Leader in the US Army. Doug served a combat tour in Iraq in 2005 shortly after attending the Army National Guard's Sniper School. Doug enlisted in 1995 and retired from the Army in 2010. Doug earned a BS in Applied Mathematics from the University of Rhode Island in 2004, and

an MS in Engineering Science with a concentration in Industrial Statistics from New Jersey Institute of Technology in 2010, and is currently continuing his graduate education at Rochester Institute of Technology's Center for Quality and Applied Statistics.

Eli S. Golden
Statistical Methods & Analysis Group
Building 92, QE&SA – Reliability Management Branch
US Army RDECOM-ARDEC
Picatinny Arsenal, NJ 07806-5000

e-mail: eli.s.golden.civ@mail.mil

Eli Golden is a Statistician in the ARDEC - Picatinny's Statistical Methods & Analysis Group, located within the Quality Engineering Directorate's Reliability Management Branch. Prior to this he worked as a Production Engineer for Small-Caliber Ammunition. He holds a BS in Mechanical Engineering with a minor in Mathematics from Lafayette College and an MS in Mechanical Engineering from Stevens Institute of Technology. He is currently pursuing a MS in Applied Statistics from New Jersey Institute of Technology.

Christopher Drake
Small-Caliber Ammunition Quality Branch
Building 65N, QE&SA
US Army RDECOM-ARDEC
Picatinny Arsenal, NJ 07806-5000

e-mail: christopher.drake4.civ@mail.mil

Christopher Drake is an Industrial Engineer at Picatinny Arsenal. During his three years at Picatinny, Chris has designed experiments and analyzed data using a variety of statistical methods to characterize and optimize weapon and munitions. Chris is currently pursuing a LSSGB certification by developing an Interactive Statistical Methodology Decision Tool, which will help guide engineers and scientists when analyzing data. Chris holds a BS from Pennsylvania State University in Industrial Engineering with a specialty in Manufacturing Systems Engineering, and is currently pursuing a MS in Applied Statistics from Rochester Institute of Technology.